

SEMANTIC SHIFTS AND LINGUOCULTURAL ASPECTS OF BEVERAGE TERMINOLOGY IN ENGLISH TRANSLATIONS OF BABURNAMA

H.S. Rahmatova

PhD Researcher, “Silk Road” International University of Tourism and Cultural Heritage

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17035224>

Abstract. *This article analyzes the linguocultural and semantic aspects of drink names in the English translations of Baburnama. The study examines the cultural features of gastronomic terminology, identifies semantic shifts and changes in meaning that occur during the translation process. The findings contribute to the comparison of Eastern and Western cultures and introduce new approaches to the field of translation studies.*

Keywords: *Baburnama, translation, beverages, semantics, linguoculturology, may, basit, chogir, sharbatchi.*

Introduction

In today’s era of globalization, the in-depth study of historical and cultural heritage and its transmission to other nations has acquired particular importance. *Baburnama*, considered one of the pearls of Eastern literature, is valued not only as a narrative of political and historical events but also as a unique source that sheds light on the lifestyle, food, and beverage culture of the people. The terminology related to gastronomy, especially different types of beverages mentioned in the work, reflects the social life, rituals, and customs of that period. During the process of translating these terms into English, numerous semantic shifts, including narrowing or broadening of meanings and cases of cultural transfer, can be observed. This, in turn, provides an opportunity to compare Eastern and Western cultures.

World literature and source studies include many important and rare monuments, memoirs, and historical-scientific works, whose significance lies in the formation of new traditions and in highlighting the distinctive features of each nation’s literature. *Baburnama* is a memoir that holds a special place in the history of world literature. Its global recognition is due not only to the historical accuracy of the events it describes but also to its role in presenting the history of literary and cultural relations between the Uzbek people and other nations, as well as the strong scientific and artistic foundation upon which it was created. This work is not only a rare historical source but also serves as an encyclopedic book that encompasses various fields of science. It vividly depicts the political, social, economic, and cultural life of Babur’s era, along with poets, historical figures, and geographic locations, including their etymologies and background.

The relevance of the topic lies in the fact that although various studies have been conducted on *Baburnama*, the semantic changes and linguocultural aspects of beverage terminology in its English translations have not been specifically analyzed. Therefore, this study contributes new findings to the fields of translation studies and linguoculturology.

Every nation and people possess unique national and cultural characteristics that distinguish them from others, which are clearly reflected in their customs, traditions, speech culture, and communication styles. Gastronomic terminology plays an important role in these processes. The vocabulary of any language related to food and drinks serves as a mirror reflecting

the social, cultural, and economic changes occurring in society at a given time. For this reason, every language forms numerous gastronomic terms that convey the traditions and customs of its people. Many of these terms encapsulate linguocultural features that express a worldview shaped through national culture and language.

In particular, the names of beverages found in *Baburnama* are not only examples of the gastronomic lexicon of that period, but also serve as important linguocultural units that illustrate the people's socio-domestic life, feast traditions, and cultural interactions. The way these terms are rendered in English translations allows for an analysis of the semantic shifts, the translator's intercultural perspective, and the extent to which the national flavor of beverage-related terms is preserved.

Gastronomic vocabulary represents an important layer of the Uzbek language's lexical richness. It reflects the national characteristics of the Uzbek people. At this point, it is worth briefly discussing the term *gastronomy*. Etymologically, "gastronomy" derives from two Greek words: *gastros* – meaning "stomach", and *nomos* – meaning "rule" or "regulation"[1]. In addition, gastronomy encompasses the preparation of food and, more broadly, the discovery, tasting, experimentation, study, understanding, and documentation of the sensory qualities of human nutrition. It also explores how eating is connected to broader cultural contexts[2,354].

Nowadays, the necessity of studying languages from the perspective of national culture, and national culture from the linguistic point of view, based on theoretical and practical scientific sources, is increasingly evident. In this regard, a linguocultural approach to studying the characteristics of language units in modern linguistics is particularly relevant. This approach includes a complex of factors that influence the system of means reflecting national characteristics of interaction and observes how cognitive development occurs. Furthermore, it represents a continuous logical development of the relationship between culture and language in linguistics[3,21].

To identify the main distinctive features of linguocultural relations, it is necessary to clarify what is meant by the term *linguoculturology* in modern linguistics. Due to growing scholarly interest in this field, the number of definitions highlighting different aspects of it is increasing. V.V. Vorobyev defines *linguoculturology* as a complex scientific field of a generalizing type that examines the interrelation and interdependence of language and culture through systematic methods and cultural structures, focusing on the structure and functioning of cultural and linguistic units[4,4].

Boburnoma can also be considered a linguistic work. The author of *Vaqoye* presents extremely engaging and profound observations in some of the most fascinating fields of linguistics—such as etymology and phonetics[5,10]. The work is regarded as a reliable source for studying the history, customs, literature, and other aspects of several peoples. This also applies to the various types of beverages mentioned in the text. In *Boburnoma*, we find terms related to drinks such as *chog'ir*, *may*, *suv*, *basit*, *sharbat*, *sharob*, *ichkilik*, and *qaynatma*. In the original version of the text, the intoxicating drink is mostly referred to as *chog'ir*, while in later versions or adaptations, it is often rendered as *may* or *sharob*[5,10].

Additionally, the word *suv* (water) is frequently used—sometimes to mean drinking water, and in other contexts, to refer to rivers, springs, or natural water sources. This variation plays an important role in uncovering the linguocultural layer embedded in *Boburnoma*. Generally, the majority of beverages mentioned in the work are intoxicating: *chog'ir*, *may*, *araq*, etc. Besides these, one can also encounter intoxicating gastronomic terms such as *basit* and *ma'jun*.

As a historical source of its time, *Boburnoma* reflects not only political and military events but also aspects of court life and cultural customs. Through detailed descriptions of Sultan Ahmad's drinking and eating habits, the work reveals his personal character, social relationships, and the subtle features of courtly culture in that era. Terms such as *ichkulukka tushar*, *chog'ir*, and *basit* provide valuable linguocultural insights into drinking customs and habits of the time.

In the original text, the author describes Sultan Ahmad as follows: "*Gohikim ichkulukka tushar erdi, yigirma-o'ttiz kun payo-pay ichar erdi. Gohikim, chog'irdin chiqar erdi, yana yigirma-o'ttiz kun ichmas edi. Bir o'lturg'on bila majlisda gohi bir kecha-kunduz o'lturur edi, yaxshi ichar edi. Chog'ir ichmas kun-lari basitni guzaro yeyar erdi. Tabiatig'a imsok g'olib edi, kamsuxan va odmi kishi erdi, ixtiyori beklari ilgida edi.*" [6,32].

Here, the expression "*ichkulukka tushar*" denotes Sultan Ahmad's habit of starting to drink and the continuity of this process. L-E translates the phrase as "drinking wine" [7,32], A.B as "settled down to drink" [8,34], while W.T renders it as "He was a good drinker" [9,53]. These translations show that not only the literal meaning of the expression but also the aspect of continuity and order in drinking is of great importance. Furthermore, while the word "*chog'ir*" is simply translated as *wine* in L-E, both A.B and W.T emphasize its contextual meaning by highlighting the duration and sequence of drinking. This demonstrates that preserving the cultural and social context plays a crucial role in translation.

The term "*basit*" refers to Sultan Ahmad's eating habits on the days he abstained from drinking. L-E translates it as "pungent substances," A.B as "ate without conviviality," and W.T as "take his meals casually." However, W.T's interpretation as "parsimony" does not fully reflect the original context, since *basit* in fact conveys a manner of eating associated with avoiding social interactions, not merely material frugality.

A linguo-cultural analysis reveals that the differences in translation are connected to the translators' approaches: Leyden–Erskine tend to emphasize lexical equivalence, Annette Susannah Beveridge aims to retain contextual and pragmatic details, while Wheeler Thackston sometimes overgeneralizes the meaning. At the same time, Sultan Ahmad's drinking and eating habits provide additional insights into his character—kind, reserved, and attentive to social customs.

In the *Baburnama*, the lexeme "*sharbatchi*" does not directly denote a type of drink but rather refers to a professional occupation. However, since it derives from the word "*sharbat*", its semantic root is directly associated with beverages. Thus, even when used as a personal designation, the lexical structure and morphology of the term preserve traces of a drink. For this reason, despite functioning as a noun of profession, the inclusion of "*sharbatchi*" in the linguo-cultural analysis of beverages is scientifically justified: "*Mirzo bila Muhammad Quli qavchin Hasan sharbatchi bila kirdilar.*" [6,32]. Translators have rendered this term differently:

1. **L-E – "sherbetchi"** [7,62]: This version reflects a phonetic adaptation of the original term, preserving its exotic color and drawing the reader closer to Babur's era. From a linguo-cultural perspective, it retains the cultural specificity of *sharbat*.

2. **Annette Susannah Beveridge – "sherbet-server"** [8,62]: Beveridge opts for an explanatory translation, where "sherbet" conveys the drink and "server" denotes the profession, thus making it comprehensible for Western readers. However, this approach weakens the national coloring, as "server" in modern English merely suggests a servant, failing to capture the *sharbatchi's* distinct social role in Babur's time.

3. **W. Thackston – "sharbatchi"** [9,71]: By transliterating the original term, this rendering preserves the cultural authenticity most fully, as it conveys not only the reference to the

beverage but also the historical and cultural connotations associated with the figure of the *sharbatchi*.

In conclusion, Leyden–Erskine’s “*sherbetchi*” prioritizes color, Beveridge’s “*sherbet-server*” prioritizes comprehensibility, while Thackston’s “*sharbatchi*” prioritizes cultural authenticity. Thus, the translations reflect different linguo-cultural strategies: one aimed at preserving national flavor, another at accessibility for the target audience, and yet another at academic precision.

Additionally, let us consider the expression in the original: “*Buxoro chog‘irlari*” [6,72]. The term “*chog‘ir*” in Babur’s era denoted a type of alcoholic drink, similar to wine (*may*, *xamr*). “*Buxoro*” is a toponym functioning adjectivally here, i.e., “*chog‘ir* specific to or originating from Bukhara.” Thus, the phrase denotes not only a beverage but also its cultural provenance—namely, the reputation of Bukhara as a viticulture center of that time.

- **Leyden–Erskine: “wine of Bokhara”** [7,85]. Semantically close to literal translation: *wine = chog‘ir, of Bokhara = from Bukhara*. From a linguo-cultural perspective, this rendering is accessible but loses the specific connotations of *chog‘ir* related to Eastern festive culture and religious perceptions. To a European reader, it becomes a simple “Bokhara wine.”

- **A. Beveridge: “Bukhara wine”** [8,83]. Semantically more concise, this adjective–noun structure (*Bukhara wine*) sounds more natural in English. Linguo-culturally, however, it resembles a commercial product or brand name (*French wine, Italian wine*), thereby obscuring the original Eastern cultural spirit.

- **W. Thackston: “Bukhara wines”** [9,87]. Here the plural form (*wines*) suggests multiple varieties, presenting Bukhara as a wine-producing center. Culturally, this translation frames the concept in Western economic terms, reducing the original Eastern atmosphere of feasts and literary culture.

Thus, Leyden–Erskine’s *wine of Bokhara* simplifies the historical text but neglects cultural nuance, Beveridge’s *Bukhara wine* is concise and natural but Westernizes the imagery, while Thackston’s *Bukhara wines* emphasizes economic categorization rather than cultural distinctiveness. In all cases, rendering “*chog‘ir*” merely as *wine* transforms Eastern festive culture into Western viniculture traditions, significantly diminishing the original cultural coloring.

In conclusion, the Baburnama not only reflects the socio-political life, customs, and cultural values of its era, but also provides valuable information on the beverages consumed at the time. Terms such as “*chog‘ir*,” “*sharbat*,” “*may*” denote more than just drinks; they encapsulate the culture of feasting, religious and moral perceptions, and gastronomic traditions of the Eastern world.

REFERENCES

1. <https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gastronomy>
2. Kivela, J. va Crotts, J.C. (2006). Turizm va gastronomiya: Turistlarning maqsadni qanday boshdan kechirishiga gastronomiyaning ta'siri. Mehmondo'stlik va turizm tadqiqotlari jurnali, 30 (3), P. 354-377
3. Evsyukova T.V. Lingvokuliturologiya. Uchebnik. 2-e izdanie. – M.: Izd «Flinta» 2014 g. – 21 s.
4. Воробьев В.В. Лингвокультуроология. Учебник. – М.: Изд РУДН. 2006 г. – 47 с.

5. Zahiriddin, Muhammad Bobur Бобурнома. Ҳозирги ўзбек тилига табдил қилганлар: Ваҳоб 79 В Rahmonov, Karomat Mullaxo'jaeva. Toshkent: "O'zbekiston" NMIU, 2019. 440 b. SBN 978-9943-25-707-8
6. UO'K: 821.512.133-3 KBK: 84(50)1 B-79 Bobur, Zahiriddin Muhammad Zahiriddin Muhammad Bobur / Boburnoma: -T.: "IJOD-PRESS", 2019. 576 b. ISBN 978-9943-5814-9-4
7. King L, Leyden J. & Erskine W. Memoirs of Zehir-ed-Din Muhammed Baber, Emperor of Hindustan. – London, 1826. Annotated and revised ed. by L. King, 2 Vols., – Milford, 1921. 480 p.
8. Beveridge A.S. The Bābur-nāma in English (Memoirs of Babur), Translated from the original Turki Text of Zahiru'ddin Muhammad Babur Padshah Ghazi by Annette Susannah Beveridge, 2 Vols., – London, 1922; Repr, in one Volume, – London, 1969; – New Delhi, 1970; – Lahore, 1975. – 472 p.
9. The Baburnama. Memoirs of Babur, Prince and Emperor, Translated, edited, and, annotated by Wheeler. M., Thackston. – New York & Oxford, 1996. – 460 p.